

1 **Fragility curve modifiers for RC dual buildings** 2 **including nonlinear site effects and SSI**

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4 We investigate the influence of soil-structure interaction (SSI) and nonlinear soil be-
5 havior on the seismic fragility of reinforced concrete (RC) dual (frame + shear wall)
6 buildings resting on shallow foundations. This paper includes a holistic methodol-
7 ogy to account for nonlinear soil behavior and soil-foundation-structure interaction
8 in a modular way. Using nonlinear dynamic analyses, we derive fragility curves
9 for a wide set of building typologies and soil profiles, showing that soil behavior
10 during strong shaking significantly affects the vulnerability of the soil - foundation
11 - structure system. The influence of soil-structure interaction is pronounced mostly
12 for soft soil profiles, varying in a building-specific way. Post-processing of our re-
13 sults evolves into a set of fragility modifiers that enable risk analysts to massively
14 account for soil-related and/or SSI effects in large-scale risk assessments.

15 **INTRODUCTION**

16 Earthquakes represent a serious threat for societies, thus, emphasis is placed on quantifying and
17 mitigating the expected damage and loss. Fragility and vulnerability curves have emerged in
18 recent years as an indispensable tool for a series of purposes associated with seismic risk man-
19 agement and resilience, such as estimation of expected losses in future earthquakes, structural
20 design and retrofit, seismic insurance, real estate valuation and business continuity. The lack of
21 adequate empirical data led to the development of analytical and hybrid methodologies ([Kappos,](#)
22 [2016](#)) for the derivation of fragility and vulnerability curves that reflect the modeler's approach,
23 with the state-of-the-art being constantly discussed and improved ([Silva et al., 2019](#)). Further-
24 more, there is an ongoing discussion about the impact of the uncertainties involved ([Silva, 2019](#);
25 [Bradley, 2013](#))

26 Earthquake vulnerability depends on a large number of structural characteristics: seismic
27 design code, structural typology and material properties, to list a few. A considerable contribu-
28 tor to vulnerability is the influence of the soil-foundation system. Nonlinear soil behavior and

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29 soil-structure interaction (SSI) effects on structures –whether beneficial or detrimental– are well
30 studied (Mylonakis and Gazetas, 2000). In general, soil tends to amplify bedrock-level ground
31 motions, while SSI might alter the structural performance because of its foundation flexibil-
32 ity (Karatzetzou and Pitilakis, 2018). In addition, geometric and material nonlinearities in the
33 soil-foundation system further modify the response of the structure, with respect to the soil
34 characteristics and the intensity of the ground motion (Pitilakis et al., 2013).

35 At present, the vast majority of analytical vulnerability studies and risk assessment are per-
36 formed assuming fixed-base conditions. While a plethora of studies highlights the importance
37 of soil-foundation effects on structures, associating these effects with fragility curves is still an
38 open topic, as clearly stated in the work of Silva et al. (2019). Saez et al. (2008) and Saez et al.
39 (2011) examined the influence of nonlinear soil behavior and SSI on the seismic performance
40 of structures, presenting their results in vulnerability terms. Rajeev and Tesfamariam (2012)
41 used an optimized Latin hypercube sampling technique to investigate the variability of fragility
42 curves, including SSI and soil uncertainties. Behnamfar and Banizadeh (2016) studied the dis-
43 tribution of seismic vulnerability in reinforced concrete (RC) structures, comparing fixed-base
44 and flexible-base models. They showed that plastic hinge development increases considerably
45 in the lower third of the buildings, especially in the case of shear wall systems. Tang and Zhang
46 (2011) investigated, in a probabilistic manner, the seismic demand imposed on a slender RC
47 shear wall based on a flexible foundation; SSI generally reduces the damage probability of the
48 shear wall, especially when soil nonlinearity is considered. Karapetrou et al. (2015) derived a
49 set of fragility curves for a 9-story RC moment resisting frame, considering both linear elas-
50 tic and nonlinear soil behavior to evaluate site and SSI effects on the corresponding fragility
51 curves; adopting two damage states, it was shown that vulnerability increases with respect to
52 the reference fixed-base model.

53 In this paper, we present and discuss fragility curves for dual RC buildings including a
54 holistic methodology to account for local nonlinear soil behavior and soil-structure interaction
55 in a modular way. Engineers are provided with fragility modifiers (FM) to modify any fragility
56 curve –for example, found in GEM (Yepes-Estrada et al., 2016)– because of nonlinear soil re-
57 sponse and/or foundation-soil compliance. In particular, we present a stepwise methodology to
58 be used in any building-specific vulnerability assessment. We adopt the incremental dynamic
59 analysis (IDA) (Vamvatsikos and Cornell, 2002, 2004), but we scale the underlying bedrock
60 ground motion to derive clouds of earthquake intensity - structural response pairs and to post-
61 process the results to obtain a wide set of fragility curves (Baker, 2015). While case-specific

62 fragility curves including SSI effects have been published, we apply our modular methodology
63 to a wide range of building models and soil profiles. This happens with a view to quantify-
64 ing local nonlinear site effects and/or SSI effects and provide an overview for large-scale risk
65 assessment procedures. The presented fragility modifiers facilitate large-scale risk assessment
66 by permitting the batch transformation of the selected fragility curves, in a simple and efficient
67 manner, to include local nonlinear site effects and/or SSI. Furthermore, this procedure can be
68 easily implemented in seismic risk assessment software, for example, modifying the median
69 values for fragility curves using the OpenQuake engine (Silva et al., 2014) or combined with
70 ShakeMaps (Silva and Horspool, 2019). Our loss curves for the flexible-base structures resting
71 upon soft soil increase substantially with respect to the fixed-base case, which is also propagated
72 in annual expected losses when employing a damage-to-loss model (Martins et al., 2016).

73 METHODOLOGY

74 Here we develop and apply a holistic methodology to account for nonlinear soil behavior and
75 soil-foundation-structure interaction within a vulnerability assessment framework.

- 76 1. The first step is the definition of each *building model*, whether it is a single building or a
77 group. While for the building-specific case the only prerequisite is the accurate definition
78 of the nonlinear numerical model, in the case of a group of buildings, an explicit taxon-
79 omy is needed. More specifically, one needs the discretization in terms of the number
80 of stories/height of the building, the lateral load-resisting structure (shear walls, moment
81 resisting frames) and the distribution of the infills – if any –, as well as the regulations of
82 the corresponding seismic code.
- 83 2. Second, soil-foundation compliance is modeled using appropriate elastic springs and
84 dashpot elements or, more elaborately, nonlinear springs to define the *foundation model*.
- 85 3. Next, ground motion is propagated from the bedrock through the soil to the free-field,
86 using either a nonlinear finite element *soil model* or a site response analysis software.
- 87 4. Since wave propagation is explicitly modeled, all the selected *ground motions* in this
88 methodology must refer to bedrock conditions (soil type A in all seismic codes). This
89 guarantees that any site effects and soil uncertainties are beforehand absent.
- 90 5. *Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA)* is qualified as the analysis method to derive a cloud
91 of earthquake intensity - structural response pairs. Particularly, IDA is conducted in three

Figure 1. Flowchart of the step-by-step research framework.

92 separate steps; (5a) *bedrock to surface propagation*, returns a set of free-field motions
 93 (FFM) for the corresponding input, next (5b) *kinematic interaction* is implemented by
 94 modifying the FFM to estimate the foundation input motion (FIM) and (iii) nonlinear
 95 dynamic analyses are run for every FIM to calculate the (5c) *structural response* of the
 96 building models.

97 6. Structural response is further associated with the *damage states (DS)*. In general, two
 98 preeminent approaches are used: (i) a drift-dependent or (ii) a strain-dependent approach,
 99 determining the required response.

100 7. Post-process of the analyses pairs estimates the probability of exceeding the predefined
 101 DS, indicating the *fragility* of each dual RC building.

102 8. Associating each DS with the level of loss/damage expected via the use of an appropriate
 103 *damage index* translates fragility into 9. *loss/vulnerability*. The flowchart in Figure 1
 104 outlines our step-by-step modular framework. Each step is explained in detail below.

105 DEFINITION OF THE BUILDING MODELS

106 We categorize buildings based on i) the number of stories (and their height), ii) the lateral load-
 107 resisting structure (shear walls and/or moment resisting frames), iii) the distribution of the infills

108 —if any, and iv) the seismic code in effect during construction. In this paper, we investigate a
109 set of nine dual (frame+shear wall) RC buildings corresponding to building typologies met in
110 practice (Kappos et al., 2006). We select buildings with a different number of stories and three
111 different configurations for each one, notably i) a bare system, ii) an unreinforced masonry
112 infilled system and iii) a system with pilotis (soft ground story). The buildings are designed
113 and analyzed assuming low and moderate seismic code provisions; however, SSI is found to
114 have similar effects on buildings regardless the code provisions. We model only regular in
115 plan buildings to facilitate large-scale risk assessment. **For the same reason and to retain the
116 generality of our method, geometric nonlinear effects are not considered as failure criteria,
117 however they are included in the modeling procedure.**

118 We use OpenSees (Mazzoni et al., 2009) to model the buildings as 2D equivalents in the
119 direction of the shear walls, using fiber elements. The uniaxial "Concrete01" and "Reinforcing-
120 Steel" materials are selected to form the fiber sections for each structural element; the "Con-
121 crete01" material object implements the modified Kent and Park concrete model (Kent and Park,
122 1971) proposed by Scott et al. (1982) with degraded linear unloading/reloading stiffness based
123 on the work of Karsan and Jirsa (1969); the "ReinforcingSteel" material object implements the
124 reinforcing steel material model, based on the backbone curve described by Chang and Mander
125 (1994). More details on the building models are provided in the appendix.

126 DEFINITION OF THE FOUNDATION MODELS

127 Inertial interaction effects are considered using two approaches: (i) three individual elastic
128 springs and dashpots (Pais and Kausel, 1988) for each footing, i.e. for the horizontal, vertical
129 and rotational degrees of freedom and (ii) Beam-on-Nonlinear-Winkler-Foundation (BNWF)
130 spring-type elements (Harden et al., 2005). The foundation modeling with BNWF elements
131 is more elaborate and thus, in the main discussion of the results, we refer only to the BNWF
132 model. Even though the BNWF approach does not come without limitations (i.e. cannot cap-
133 ture permanent settlements and rotations, complex kinematic and inertial effects etc.), it is pop-
134 ular because of its simplicity and predictive abilities on a variety of problems NIST (2012).
135 The corresponding fixed-base-on-rock models are used as a reference, representing the current
136 state-of-practice.

137 The "ShallowFoundationGen" command in OpenSees creates the BNWF model, introduc-
138 ing a set of closely spaced independent nonlinear springs, coupled with a dashpot and gap

139 elements. This dashpot includes hysteretic and radiation damping. Vertical springs distributed
140 along the base of the footing aim to capture the **transient** rocking, uplift and settlement, whereas
141 horizontal springs attached to the sides of the footing are used to capture the resistance against
142 sliding and passive pressure. [Raychowdhury and Hutchinson \(2009\)](#) and [Harden and Hutchin-
143 son \(2009\)](#) calibrated the BNWF model parameters against centrifuge experiments **for models
144 with sand or medium to stiff soil clay**, while [Gajan et al. \(2010\)](#) reviewed the implemented
145 model in OpenSees. **Despite this limitation in the soil materials, the BNWF has since been
146 extensively used for clays** ([Allotey and El Naggar, 2003](#); [Kramer, 2014](#); [Tomeo et al., 2018](#)).

147 **DEFINITION OF THE SOIL MODELS**

148 A plain yet efficient scheme for an incremental dynamic analysis is to model the soil domain as
149 a pseudo-1D equivalent of its physical counterpart, and run total stress analyses (i.e. neglect-
150 ing the presence of water) defining a soil column of two-dimensional "Quad" elements using
151 OpenSees . To approach the 1D behavior, both nodes at each depth are assigned an equal degree
152 of freedom constraint. In that way, fully nonlinear soil behavior is enabled depending on the
153 selected soil material constitutive law. A single zeroLength element is placed at the base of the
154 soil column, parallel to the soil model base, to define the dashpot ([Lysmer and Kuhlemeyer,
155 1969](#)). Base nodes are fixed with respect to their vertical degree of freedom, while for the hor-
156 izontal degree of freedom we assign an equal degree of freedom constraint **connected to the
157 dashpot**. Consequently, the input motion at the base of the soil column is defined in velocity
158 terms, while the resulting force is obtained by multiplying the known velocity time series by a
159 constant factor set as the product of the area of the soil column base with the mass density and
160 the shear wave velocity of the underlying bedrock. The mesh dimensions are determined by
161 ensuring that ten elements fit within each wavelength of the propagating shear waves according
162 to ([Kuhlemeyer and Lysmer, 1973](#)), for the lowest shear wave velocity waves propagating at a
163 maximum frequency of engineering interest of 10Hz.

164 1D ground response analyses are known to be able to reproduce only certain site effects,
165 mainly related to local soil response ([Stewart et al., 2017](#)). As such, they might underestimate
166 response at longer periods, related to surface waves, basin effects and other multi-dimensional
167 phenomena, and therefore have to be used with caution. Nevertheless, 1D ground response
168 analyses remain the most frequently utilized procedure.

169 GROUND MOTIONS SELECTION

170 A prerequisite for the accurate earthquake risk assessment of structures is the wise selection of
171 a set of earthquake recordings. Suites of ground motions exist in literature (Baker and Shahi,
172 2011), appropriately selected for vulnerability assessment purposes. This selection is usually
173 based on the method of analysis. Currently, there are three prevailing procedures to correlate En-
174 gineering Demand Parameters (EDP) and Intensity Measures (IM) in the fragility calculations:
175 (i) the Incremental Dynamic Analysis, (ii) the Multiple-Stripe Analysis and (iii) the Cloud Anal-
176 ysis. A thorough review of these alternatives can be found in Miano et al. (2018). The first two
177 alternatives may involve record scaling to match a conditional spectrum-based ground motion
178 (Kohrangi et al., 2017), while the third uses unscaled earthquake records (Jalayer et al., 2017).
179 Nevertheless, none of the above-mentioned procedures accounts –at least in a straight-forward
180 way– for soil nonlinearity.

181 In the methodology that we propose, the earthquake records are purposely selected from
182 recordings at bedrock (or type A soil in all codes), eliminating this way any site effects and soil
183 uncertainties on the free-field motion. Furthermore, any recordings from the same earthquake
184 are excluded to derive a set of independent records. All the selected seismic events have $M_w >$
185 5.5. This filtering procedure is rather exhausting for the existing strong motion databases since
186 only a limited number of such records is available. The procedure is followed by an iterative
187 routine which attempts to match a given target spectrum, for example the EC8 spectrum in the
188 illustrative application that follows, and further eliminates a number of records to converge,
189 reaching a mean spectrum of the remaining records that closely matches the target.

190 INCREMENTAL DYNAMIC ANALYSIS

191 Incremental dynamic analysis (Vamvatsikos and Cornell, 2002, 2004) is performed to derive a
192 cloud of IM and EDP pairs, subsequently post-processed to generate the corresponding fragility
193 curves. In fact, any other compatible nonlinear dynamic analysis scheme can be used. Choosing
194 the PGA on A-type soil as the IM facilitates highlighting SSI and local site effects because of
195 nonlinear soil behavior.

196 Wave propagation from bedrock to surface

197 Each bedrock motion is properly scaled according to the desired IDA levels, and applied as
198 the input motion at the base of the 2D soil columns described above, eventually returning a set

199 of free-field motions (FFM) for each original recording. Nonlinear soil behavior is inherently
200 accounted for because of the corresponding constitutive law in OpenSees.

201 **Kinematic interaction effects**

202 Foundation input motion and free-field motion may differ because of kinematic interaction, in
203 which stiff foundation elements placed at or below the ground surface force foundation motions
204 to deviate from free-field motions due to base slab averaging, wave scattering, and embedment
205 effects. The relationship between free-field and foundation input motions is defined by a transfer
206 function that estimates the ratio between foundation and free-field motion in the frequency
207 domain. Here, the foundation input motion (FIM) is calculated including kinematic interaction
208 effects, following [NIST \(2012\)](#) for every single FFM from the previous step. For wave passage
209 effects we used the equations of [Mylonakis et al. \(2006\)](#) and for embedment effect the equations
210 of [Kausel et al. \(1978\)](#).

211 **Building response**

212 For every single FIM (and FFM as reference case), a nonlinear dynamic analysis is run to
213 calculate building response using the FIM as base excitation for the building models resting
214 on the two foundation models (elastic springs and BNWF) described above. To describe both
215 structural and non-structural damage, the response is calculated in terms of (i) interstory drift
216 ratio (IDR), (ii) floor acceleration, (iii) floor displacement, (iv) column curvature and (v) base
217 reaction.

218 **DAMAGE STATES**

219 Next, we need an accurate definition of the damage states (DS) for the buildings. While this
220 becomes often a subjective issue ([Hill and Rossetto, 2008](#)), various drift-dependent or strain-
221 dependent damage state definitions exist in the literature regarding RC structures ([Rossetto and](#)
222 [Elnashai, 2003](#); [Ghobarah, 2004](#); [Crowley et al., 2004](#); [Kappos et al., 2006](#)), the global use
223 of the corresponding fragility models practically impossible. On the contrary and in order to
224 achieve broader applicability of our results, here we focus on quantifying the differences be-
225 tween fixed-base and flexible-base models rather than presenting a set of case-specific fragility
226 curves. We used the [Rossetto and Elnashai \(2003\)](#) and [Ghobarah \(2004\)](#) drift-based damage
227 states as benchmarks to **iteratively** approach the fragility curves published by [Kappos et al.](#)
228 [\(2003\)](#) and [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) for the same fixed-base models. [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) used a

229 hybrid method for estimating the fragility curves of buildings, where they calibrated the fragility
 230 curves based on inspection of actually damaged structures. As the fragility curves calculated
 231 by the hybrid method in [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) might incorporate implicitly, to a certain degree,
 232 local site effects and SSI, exact matching with our curves should not be expected; yet we obtain
 233 a well-constrained set of limit state values bounded by the adopted literature. Besides, since
 234 hereafter we focus on the differences between fixed- and flexible-based fragility curves, the
 235 influence of the damage state definition is minimized.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Percentile modelling difference between the BNWF and the fixed-base over the fixed-base with increasing bedrock acceleration of the Western Tottori/Japan record (a) and App.Lucano/Italy record (b), in terms of maximum IDR and maximum ground floor column curvature ratios for the 4-story, bare structure.

236 The use of drift-based limit values for both fixed-base and flexible-base structures is accom-
 237 panied by the corresponding column curvature, demonstrating that drift and curvature model-to-

238 model fluctuations follow the same path, i.e. they can be used interchangeably. Both interstory
 239 drift and moment-curvature are recorded during the analyses for all the vertical elements to
 240 show that both global maxima increase or decrease proportionally and simultaneously along
 241 the acceleration axis, i.e. when drift increases, curvature increases accordingly, and vice versa.
 242 The reason behind this additional comparison is that curvature, and consequently strain devel-
 243 opment at sectional level, are directly associated with structural damage, while one may expect
 244 that drift at ground floor is triggered by foundation rotation. Furthermore, we observe that –for
 245 all the cases examined here– foundation rotation accounts for less than 10% of the total IDR,
 246 indicating that the structural deformation counterpart is large enough to justify damage devel-
 247 opment. Again, it is underlined that we focus on the differences observed between the derived
 248 fragility curves, thus a more refined definition of the limit states values is unnecessary. Figure 2
 249 shows the differences between the BNWF and the fixed-base model in terms of both maximum
 250 IDR and maximum ground floor column curvature ratios for two different earthquake records
 251 at bedrock, scaled from 0.05g to 1.0g.

252 **FRAGILITY CURVES**

253 The results of the conducted analyses are statistically post-processed to derive the corresponding
 254 fragility curves. Fragility curves represent the probability of exceeding a predefined limit state,
 255 as a function of an engineering demand parameter, under a seismic excitation of given intensity.
 256 Equation 1 describes the cumulative conditional probability of exceeding a DS for a given IM
 257 (Ibarra and Krawinkler, 2005).

$$P[DS|IM] = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(IM) - \ln(\overline{IM})}{\beta}\right) \quad (1)$$

258 where Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function, IM is the intensity measure
 259 of the earthquake, \overline{IM} is the corresponding median value, β is the log-standard deviation and
 260 DS is the damage state. In detail, the log-standard deviation parameter characterizes the total
 261 dispersion related to each fragility curve. Three primary sources of uncertainty which contribute
 262 to the total variability of any given limit state are considered (FEMA-NIBS, 2004): (i) the
 263 variability related to the definition of the limit state value, (ii) the capacity of each structural
 264 model and (iii) the seismic demand. The log-standard deviation referring to the definition of
 265 the limit states is equal to 0.40, whereas the corresponding value regarding the capacity is
 266 assumed equal to 0.30 for no/low seismic code structural systems (FEMA-NIBS, 2004). The
 267 latter source of uncertainty associated with the seismic demand is explicitly evaluated estimating

Figure 3. Typical 4-story RC dual bare building.

Table 1. Indicative properties of the buildings selected.

Selected buildings : Properties			
Seismic code	No/Low	Typical story height	3.0m
Concrete grade	B225	Span length (Low/Mid-rise)	4.0m
Longitudinal reinforcement grade	StIII	Span length (High-rise)	6.0m
Transverse reinforcement grade	StI	Typical beam size (Low/Mid-rise)	20/60cm
Transverse reinforcement spacing	Sparse	Typical beam size (High-rise)	25/70cm
Ground story height	4.5m	Typical column size	Varies w/ height

268 the dispersion for the logarithms of PGA – maxIDR pairs, with respect to the regression method
 269 utilized, usually assuming a log-normal distribution of the data.

270 ILLUSTRATIVE NUMERICAL APPLICATION

271 DEFINITION OF THE BUILDING MODELS

272 We select three different buildings, a 2-story, a 4-story and a 9-story building, resting on a clayey
 273 soil profile. All three buildings are modeled with the three different structural configurations
 274 mentioned above, i.e. i) a bare system, ii) an infilled system and iii) with pilotis (soft ground
 275 story). Structural configuration was based on the work of [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#), representing
 276 typical structures found in Southern European countries (i.e. (older low-code buildings that
 277 typically rest on shallow foundations on individual spread footings)). Table 1 shows some
 278 indicative properties of the buildings. Figure 3 shows a typical 4-story RC dual bare building.

Table 2. Shear wave velocity of the examined soil profiles.

No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
$V_{s,30}$ (m/s)	>800	450	360	300	250	180	150
Cohesion (kPa)	-	115	85	75	56	33	28
Soil mass density (kPa)	2.0	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.5	1.4

279 DEFINITION OF THE SOIL PROFILES

280 We select seven soil profiles characterized by different shear wave velocities and 30m depth,
281 covering the range from very stiff to very soft clay, in qualitative terms. The characteristics of
282 these soil profiles affect the stiffness and damping of the geotechnical part of the foundation,
283 i.e. the foundation–soil system as discussed in [NIST \(2012\)](#). Two-dimensional "Quad" elements
284 are used to model a pseudo-1D equivalent of the free-field using OpenSees. Soil nonlinearity is
285 inherently considered by use of the "PressureIndependMultiYield" (PIMY) soil material ([Yang
286 et al., 2008](#)), varying the shear modulus, the bulk modulus, the cohesion, the octahedral shear
287 strain at which the maximum shear strength is reached and the saturated soil mass density.
288 Water table level is not defined in the analyses. [Table 2](#) presents the soil profiles examined in
289 this study with respect to their corresponding shear wave velocity $V_{s,30}$.

290 GROUND MOTION SELECTION

291 We select a set of eleven real earthquake recordings following the suggestions of [FEMA P-58
292 \(2012\)](#) and [D’Ayala et al. \(2013\)](#), referring to eleven independent seismic events and stations,
293 all recorded on sites classified as soil type A following the EC8 system ([EN-1998, 2005](#)), with
294 $V_{s,30}$ higher than 800m/s. These eleven earthquake records are shown in [Table 3](#), and their
295 response spectra in [Figure 4](#). Each bedrock recording is scaled from 0.05g to 1g and applied as
296 input motion at the base of the soil models defined above. Subsequently, this set creates 1540
297 FFM (indicative response spectra can be found in the appendix).

Table 3. List of real earthquake records

No.	Location	Database Code	R_{epi} (km)	M_w	PGA (m/s ²)	$V_{s,30}$ (m/s)	Soil Type (EC8)
1	Tabas/Iran	ESMD_59	12.00	7.35	3.16	826.00	A
2	Montenegro/Montenegro	ISESD_223	21.00	6.90	1.77	1083.00	A
3	App.Lucano/Italy	ITACA_614	9.80	5.60	1.62	1024.00	A
4	Kobe/Japan	NGA_1108	25.40	6.90	2.85	1043.00	A
5	Sierra Madre/Mexico	NGA_1645	6.46	5.61	2.71	821.69	A
6	Loma Prieta/USA	NGA_3548	20.35	6.93	4.12	1070.34	A
7	Whittier Narrows/USA	NGA_680	13.85	5.99	1.10	969.07	A
8	Northridge/USA	NGA_994	25.42	6.69	2.84	1015.88	A
9	Izmit/Turkey	T-NSMP_1109	3.40	7.60	1.65	826.11	A
10	East Sicily/Italy	ITACA_314	28.30	5.60	0.61	871.00	A
11	Western Tottori/Japan	KIK-Net_3775	31.37	6.60	1.55	967.27	A

Figure 4. Response spectra for the selected ground motions; mean response spectrum; EC8 response spectrum for soil type A.

298 BUILDING RESPONSE

299 SSI effects on dual structural systems have already been addressed in design codes (ATC, 1996),
 300 as discussed in Harden et al. (2006) and Raychowdhury (2011). In particular, emphasis is given
 301 on the “damage transfer” effect (Figure 5) caused by flexible foundations. In a typical fixed-base
 302 dual system, the shear wall counterpart is stiffer than the frame and hence tends to attract the

303 largest fraction of the lateral loads, while in a flexible-base system, large displacement demands
304 tend to damage the frame counterpart.

305 To quantify this effect, we calculate and present the wall-to-total base reactions, comparing
306 fixed-base and flexible-base models. To date, no references were found regarding this effect in
307 vulnerability terms. In particular, base reactions in terms of base moment and base shear were
308 recorded during all the conducted analyses. Next, the ratios between the wall base reaction and
309 the total base reaction were calculated for the investigated building models, and plotted against
310 the normalized duration of each recording (normalized with respect to its total duration). We
311 also estimated the mean values between 0.2 and 0.8 of the normalized duration. This happens
312 because our earthquake recordings have nearly zero amplitude for normalized timestamps lower
313 than 0.2 or greater than 0.8 of the normalized duration. Besides, toward the end of the dynamic
314 loading, reactions are mainly triggered by gravity loads, which means that the load distribution
315 differs from the dynamic lateral load case of the strong cycles of an earthquake. Fixed-base
316 and flexible-base models are compared, showing that wall-to-total base reaction ratios drop
317 significantly when SSI effects are included, implying damage transfer from the wall to the frame
318 structural counterpart. Figure 6 presents these ratios for a 2-story (top), a 4-story (middle) and
319 a 9-story (bottom) RC dual bare model, in terms of base reaction moment. Similar results have
320 been observed for base shear ratios.

321 Based on the mean values (dashed lines) derived from the dense analyses clouds (Figure 6),
322 we observe a constant drop regarding the fraction of the lateral loads attracted by the shear wall
323 counterpart. In essence, in softer soils the frame component of the structural system receives
324 an increased fraction of the total lateral load; we consider this consistent trend a "numerical
325 witness" of the effect schematically shown in Figure 5. For flexible-base systems, the wall-to-
326 total base reaction ratios range between 60% and 80% for low- and mid-rise buildings, while
327 these ratios drop below 60% for higher structures, as apparently foundation flexibility tends to
328 cancel a greater part of their lateral stiffness because of rocking, via transfer of larger load to
329 the frame structure.

330 **FRAGILITY CURVES**

331 Figure 7 presents the fragility curves derived for the 4-story regularly infilled RC structure, con-
332 sidering SSI and nonlinear soil behavior effects for soft and medium clay (top: $V_{s,30} = 180m/s$
333 and bottom: $V_{s,30} = 300m/s$). We adopted four damage states, namely SD: Slight damage,

Figure 5. Effect of foundation flexibility on the component response of a structure. In a typical fixed-base dual system (left), the shear wall counterpart is stiffer than the frame and hence tends to attract the largest fraction of the lateral loads, while in a flexible-base system (right), large displacement demands tend to damage the frame counterpart.

Adapted from: [ATC \(1996\)](#); enhancement: [Raychowdhury \(2011\)](#).

334 MD: Moderate damage, ED: Extensive damage, CD: Complete damage. The fragility curves
 335 presented are plotted alongside [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) curves, referring to the same structural
 336 typologies. However, [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#) used recordings from past Greek earthquakes with-
 337 out a soil-specific refinement, performed nonlinear static/dynamic analyses and combined the
 338 results with statistical data to approach the fragility curves, subsequently derived, in a hybrid
 339 manner. In this work, we performed an extensive set of nonlinear incremental dynamic analyses
 340 adopting various subsoil profiles, using bedrock ground motion recordings exclusively to refine
 341 our results. PGA at bedrock level is used as the intensity measure, thus nonlinear soil and SSI
 342 effects are inherent within our fragility curves. In addition, fragility curves are also derived
 343 including nonlinear soil behavior effects for both fixed-base and flexible-base models to isolate
 344 SSI effects. Nonlinear soil effects and ground motion amplifications are more preminent on
 345 the fragility curves, compared with SSI-only influence. The resulting fragility curves of our
 346 work are not directly comparable with the ones derived by [Kappos et al. \(2006\)](#), since the latter
 347 refer to generic soil conditions, i.e. we do not have the same reference PGA. However, from
 348 a qualitative point of view, as we see in [Figure 7](#), nonlinear soil behavior and SSI generally
 349 increase the probability of exceeding a damage state. Softer soil profiles generally intensify
 350 soil-related effects, mainly observed at lower (SD, MD) damage states.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6. Cloud of shear wall-to-total base reaction moment ratios in normalized duration for fixed-base and BNWF models, for all PGA at bedrock increments and different soil shear wave velocity ranging from 150m/s to 450m/s, for a 2-story (a), a 4-story (b) and a 9-story (c) RC dual building. With straight lines are the mean values for the different foundation flexibility cases.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Fragility curves for the 4-story infilled structure, considering SSI and NL soil behavior effects for soil type 6: $V_{s,30}=180\text{m/s}$ ((a), dashed) and soil type 4: $V_{s,30}=300\text{m/s}$ ((b), dashed); Kappos et al. (2006) corresponding, not soil-specific curves. SD:Slight damage, MD:Moderate damage, ED:Extensive damage, CD:Complete damage.

351

FRAGILITY MODIFIERS FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

352 While nonlinear subsoil behavior and SSI effects are significant for building-specific fragility
 353 curves, it is practically impossible to evaluate these effects for a larger scale (e.g. city-scale)
 354 risk assessment (Rovithis et al., 2017). Here we examine these effects on the typologies of RC
 355 dual buildings met in common engineering practice and propose appropriate *fragility modifiers*
 356 (*FM*) upon the existing fragility curves; risk analysts need to *modify*, rather than *re-calculate*
 357 the fragility curves.

358 We estimate the PGA corresponding to 50% probability of exceeding each DS, hereafter

359 called *median PGA* to exceed each DS from the derived fragility curves and we calculate the
 360 ratios between the (i) “flexible-base on soil” and “fixed-base on rock” models, to include local
 361 nonlinear site effects and SSI, and (ii) “flexible-base on soil” and “fixed-base on soil” models,
 362 to isolate SSI effects. In essence, ratios less than unity imply detrimental nonlinear soil and/or
 363 SSI effects, while ratios greater than unity imply favorable influence. Equation 2 describes the
 364 estimation of the FM.

$$FM_i = \frac{PGA_{50\%,flexible-base,i}}{PGA_{50\%,fixed-base,i}} \quad (2)$$

365 in which, i loops over Slight Damage (SD), Moderate Damage (MD), Extensive Damage (ED)
 366 and Complete Damage (CD), $PGA_{50\%,flexible-base}$ is the peak ground acceleration at the under-
 367 lying bedrock corresponding to 50% probability of the flexible-base-on-soil model to exceed a
 368 given damage state i , and $PGA_{50\%,fixed-base}$ is its fixed-base counterpart. Figure 8 presents the
 369 ratios for the first case (i), in the form of a heat map, grouped in four intervals for each damage
 370 state (NL+SSI). Table 4 presents the ratios for the second case (ii), i.e. net SSI effects, rounded
 371 appropriately for practical use (SSI-only).

372 We observe that site amplification and SSI effects combined lead to increased vulnerability.
 373 These effects are more pronounced in lower damage state, mainly because of higher amplifica-
 374 tion ratios between the free-field and the bedrock for low PGA values, in contrast with slight
 375 or no amplifications observed for high PGA values, as clearly seen in the indicative free-field
 376 response spectra in the appendix. Furthermore, lower damage state are more sensitive to even
 377 slight changes introduced by SSI effects, since they are defined by low interstory drift values
 378 and include a great portion of the non-structural damage, which is mainly drift-sensitive. For
 379 example, using the heat map of Figure 8 for a 4-story bare building resting on a soil profile
 380 characterized by $V_{s,30}=250\text{m/s}$, we estimate a median PGA of exceeding SD and MD equal to
 381 50%-70% of the median PGA for the fixed-base on rock model required to exceed the same
 382 damage state. Respectively, we estimate 70%-85% for the ED damage state and 85%-100% for
 383 the CD damage state.

Figure 8. Heat map: "Flexible-base on soil" to "Fixed-base on rock" ratios of median PGA to exceed each DS, described as fragility modifier (FM) in Equation 2. The discretization is based on the height of the structure (low, medium, high), the infill type (no, regular, pilotis), the damage state (slight, moderate, extensive, complete) and the soil shear wave velocity. Darker color implies stronger influence of soil nonlinearity and SSI.

384 One might notice in Figure 8 that the effect of soil nonlinearity and SSI is somewhat smaller
 385 as the building height and the damage state increase. With respect to the soil nonlinearity, this
 386 might be attributed to the inadequacy of 1D ground response analyses (used in this study) to cor-
 387 rectly reproduce complex wave propagation phenomena related to longer periods. These longer
 388 period pulses are more relevant for taller structures and heavily damaged structures which have
 389 undergone period elongation. In case basin effects or/and other two- and three-dimensional
 390 topographic phenomena are prevalent, use of Table 4 is advised.

Table 4. "Flexible-base on soil" to "Fixed-base on soil" ratios of median PGA to exceed each DS, described as fragility modifier (FM) in Equation 2. The discretization is based on the height of the structure (low, medium, high), the infill type (no, regular, pilotis), the damage state (slight, moderate, extensive, complete) and the soil shear wave velocity $V_{s,30}$. Values around 1.00 imply no/negligible influence of SSI, values lower than 1.00 imply increased vulnerability due to SSI and values greater than 1.00 correspond to favorable SSI effects.

Height	DS Infill	$V_{s,30}$	Slight				Moderate				Extensive				Complete			
			300	250	180	150	300	250	180	150	300	250	180	150	300	250	180	150
Low	No		0.80	0.70	0.70	0.65	0.85	0.85	0.65	0.65	0.75	0.70	0.75	0.75	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80
	Regular		0.80	0.70	0.65	0.65	1.00	0.80	0.70	0.65	0.80	0.70	0.75	0.75	0.80	0.75	0.75	0.75
	Pilotis		1.00	0.70	0.70	0.65	1.00	1.00	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.75	1.00	0.80	0.70	0.70
Mid	No		1.00	1.00	0.70	0.65	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.70	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.65	1.00	0.85	0.80	0.80
	Regular		1.00	0.80	0.65	0.65	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.70	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.80
	Pilotis		1.00	0.75	0.65	0.60	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.70	1.00	0.80	0.70	0.65	1.00	0.85	0.80	0.75
High	No		1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.00	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Regular		1.00	1.00	1.00	0.80	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.85	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.85	0.75
	Pilotis		1.00	1.00	1.00	0.85	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.70	1.00	1.00	0.85	0.70	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.80

391 For soil deposits characterized by shear wave velocities greater than 300m/s, structure-to-
392 soil stiffness ratio $h/(V_s T)$ drops below 0.1, thus, SSI effects have a negligible influence on
393 the vulnerability assessment (Stewart et al., 1999a,b). We observe that mainly the stiffer Low-
394 and Mid-rise buildings suffer from SSI-induced damage. SSI effects relocate, in most cases,
395 the maximum interstory drift from higher floors to the ground story. For example, using Table
396 4 we can isolate the influence of SSI on fragility. For a flexible-base 4-story, bare building
397 resting on a soil profile characterized by $V_{s,30}=180\text{m/s}$ we estimate a median PGA of exceeding
398 SD equal to 70% of the median PGA for the fixed-base structure on the same soil conditions.
399 The former model includes SSI effects, the latter does not, while both models contain any site
400 amplifications observed.

401 APPLICABILITY OF THE PROPOSED FM

402 The idea behind the FM is to shift the existing fragility curves for fixed-base structures by mul-
403 tiplying the median value for each DS with an appropriate modifier. Total variability changes
404 negligibly between the fixed-base and the flexible-base models, thus the analyst may use the
405 standard deviation of the existing fragility curves. The FM presented here cover an extensive,
406 yet not exhaustive, set of RC building typologies, as well as a set of typical soil profiles. Thus,
407 different FM will be required for different building types, particular soil stratigraphies, etc.
408 Based on our analyses, we propose:

Figure 9. Loss curves using (i) Kappos et al. (2006) fragility curve and damage index as reference, (ii) NL+SSI FM on the reference curve, (iii) EN1998 amplification factors & SSI-only FM on the reference curve, (iv) NEHRP amplification factors & SSI-only FM on the reference curve; 4-story regularly infilled dual RC structure, resting on soil with $V_{s,30}=180\text{m/s}$. For the NL+SSI case, the FM for each damage state are: SD=0.35, MD=0.63, ED=0.63, CD=0.82; for the SSI-only case, the FM are: SD=0.65, MD=0.75, ED=0.80, CD=0.80.

409 (i) FM that include both nonlinear soil behavior and SSI effects (NL+SSI, Figure 8). These
 410 modifiers permit the development of a hazard scenario referring to the underlying bedrock and
 411 appropriately shift the fragility curves with respect to the subsoil conditions for the consequent
 412 risk assessment.

413 (ii) FM that account for SSI effects only (SSI-only, Table 4). The development of a hazard
 414 scenario is usually followed by a refinement of the expected PGA (or any IM considered) with
 415 respect to the soil profiles met in the region of interest. Typically, the analyst uses microzonation
 416 studies and amplifies the PGA using amplification factors found in the seismic codes and/or
 417 literature. In this case, the use of SSI-only fragility modifiers is suggested.

418 As an extension of the presented illustrative numerical application, we derive sets of vul-
 419 nerability curves using (i) Kappos et al. (2006) fragility curves as reference curves, (ii) our
 420 NL+SSI FM applied upon the reference curves, (iii) EN1998 site amplification factors & our
 421 SSI-only FM on the reference curves and (iv) NEHRP site amplification factors & our SSI-only
 422 FM applied upon the existing reference fragility curves, adopting the central value of the corre-
 423 sponding damage index for each damage state (i.e. DS_i), equal to 0.05, 0.20, 0.45 and 0.80 for
 424 the SD, MD, ED and CD damage states, respectively. Figure 9 shows the corresponding loss
 425 curves for cases (i)-(iv), for the 4-story regularly infilled dual RC structure, resting on soil with
 426 $V_{s,30}=180\text{m/s}$. In all cases, site amplification and SSI seem to increase loss ratio.

CONCLUSIONS

428 We examined a comprehensive set of dual system RC building typologies and soil profiles to
429 derive the corresponding fragility curves and highlight the differences that occur because of
430 nonlinear soil behavior and SSI. A step-wise modular methodology is also presented to provide
431 an explicit way of including soil-related effects in risk assessment, focusing on the use of ground
432 motions recorded on bedrock, soil models to transfer the motion to the free-field and BNWF
433 (nonlinear) springs to model inertial SSI.

434 The results of this study bridge the gap between building-specific and large-scale risk as-
435 sessment by providing two sets of FM that can massively adapt existing fragility curves to
436 account for specific site amplification and/or SSI effects. Foundation flexibility causes transfer
437 of a significant fraction of the lateral seismic load from the shear wall to its frame counterpart,
438 which leads to additional damage to the RC frame component of the dual system. For flexible-
439 base systems, the wall-to-total base reaction ratios range between 60% and 80% for low- and
440 mid-rise buildings, while these ratios drop below 60% for taller structures. This phenomenon
441 is further reflected on the derived fragility curves, using both maximum interstory drift and
442 curvature as damage indicators.

443 We present an illustrative example, applying our methodology and discussing the results.
444 Our illustrative fragility and loss curves show that soil plays an important role in risk assess-
445 ment. The influence of the soil-foundation flexibility is important mostly for soft soil profiles
446 leading to increased vulnerability, in most cases, while it gradually fades away for stiffer soils.
447 Soil amplifies the ground motion and this effect is reflected on the increased vulnerability of
448 the system (i.e. the structure and the soil). Moreover, ground motion amplification influences
449 fragility curves to a larger extent than SSI effects alone; SSI effects alone also lead to increased
450 vulnerability for dual RC buildings in most cases, mainly because of the damage transfer effect
451 from the wall to the frame.

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459 REFERENCES

- 460 Allotey, N. and El Naggar, M. H., 2003. Analytical moment–rotation curves for rigid foundations
461 based on a Winkler model. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* **23**, 367–381. doi:10.1016/
462 S0267-7261(03)00034-4.
- 463 ATC, 1996. *ATC-40. Seismic Evaluation and Retrofit of Concrete Buildings, volumes 1 and 2. Tech.*
464 *Rep. 94-0006*, Redwood City, CA.
- 465 Baker, J. W., 2015. Efficient Analytical Fragility Function Fitting Using Dynamic Structural Analysis.
466 *Earthquake Spectra* **31**, 579–599.
- 467 Baker, J. W. and Shahi, S. K., 2011. *New Ground Motion Selection Procedures and Selected Motions*
468 *for the PEER Transportation Research Program. Tech. rep.*
- 469 Behnamfar, F. and Banizadeh, M., 2016. Effects of soil-structure interaction on distribution of seismic
470 vulnerability in RC structures. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* **80**, 73–86.
- 471 Bradley, B. A., 2013. A critical examination of seismic response uncertainty analysis in earthquake
472 engineering. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* **42**, 1717–1729.
- 473 Chang, G. A. and Mander, J. B., 1994. Seismic Energy Based Fatigue Damage Analysis of Bridge
474 Columns:Part 1-Evaluation of Seismic Capacity. *NCEER Tech. Rep. No. NCEER-94-0006* p. 230.
- 475 Crowley, H., Pinho, R., and Bommer, J., 2004. A probabilistic displacement-based vulnerability assess-
476 ment procedure for earthquake loss estimation. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* **2**, 173–219.
- 477 Das, B., 1981. *Principles of Foundation Engineering*. Prentice Hall.
- 478 Das, B., 1983. *Advanced Soil Mechanics*. Taylor and Francis Publisher.
- 479 D’Ayala, D., Meslem, A., Vamvatsikos, D., Porter, K., Rossetto, T., Crowley, H., and Silva, V., 2013.
480 Guidelines for Analytical Vulnerability Assessment - Low/Mid-Rise. *GEM Technical Report* **08**, 162.
- 481 EN-1998, 2005. *Eurocode 8: Design of structures for earthquake resistance. Tech. rep.*
- 482 FEMA-NIBS, 2004. *Multi-hazard loss estimation methodology: Earthquake model: HAZUS MH Tech-*
483 *nical Manual. Tech. Rep. Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center, Washington, DC, USA.*
- 484 FEMA P-58, 2012. *Seismic Performance Assessment of Buildings - methodology. Tech. Rep. September.*
- 485 Gajan, S., Raychowdhury, P., Hutchinson, T. C., Kutter, B. L., and Stewart, J. P., 2010. Application and
486 validation of practical tools for nonlinear soil-foundation interaction analysis. *Earthquake Spectra*
487 **26**, 111–129.
- 488 Ghobarah, A., 2004. On drift limits associated with different damage levels. *International workshop on*
489 *performance-based seismic design concepts and implementation* pp. 321–332.
- 490 Harden, C., Hutchinson, T., Martin, G. R., and Kutter, B. L., 2005. *Numerical Modeling of the Nonlinear*
491 *Cyclic Response of Shallow Foundations. Tech. rep.*
- 492 Harden, C., Hutchinson, T., and Moore, M., 2006. Investigation into the Effects of Foundation Uplift on
493 Simplified Seismic Design Procedures. *Earthquake Spectra* **22**, 663–692.
- 494 Harden, C. W. and Hutchinson, T. C., 2009. Beam-on-nonlinear-winkler-foundation modeling of shal-
495 low, rocking-dominated footings. *Earthquake Spectra* **25**, 277–300.
- 496 Hill, M. and Rossetto, T., 2008. Comparison of building damage scales and damage descriptions for use
497 in earthquake loss modelling in Europe. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* **6**, 335–365.
- 498 Holtz, R. and Kovacs, W., 1981. *An Introduction to Geotechnical Engineering*. Prentice Hall.

499 Ibarra, L. F. and Krawinkler, H., 2005. *Global Collapse of Frame Structures under Seismic Excitations*.
500 *Tech. rep.*

501 Jalayer, F., Ebrahimian, H., Miano, A., Manfredi, G., and Sezen, H., 2017. Analytical fragility assess-
502 ment using unscaled ground motion records. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics* **46**,
503 2639–2663.

504 Kappos, A., 2016. An overview of the development of the hybrid method for seismic vulnerability
505 assessment of buildings. *Structure and Infrastructure Engineering* **12**, 1573–1584.

506 Kappos, A. J., Panagiotopoulos, C., Panagopoulos, G., and Papadopoulos, E., 2003. *WP4 - Reinforced*
507 *concrete buildings (level I and II analysis). RISK-UE project: An advanced approach to earthquake*
508 *risk scenarios with applications to different European towns. Tech. rep.*

509 Kappos, A. J., Panagopoulos, G., Panagiotopoulos, C., and Penelis, G., 2006. A hybrid method for the
510 vulnerability assessment of R/C and URM buildings. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* **4**, 391–413.

511 Karapetrou, S., Fotopoulou, S., and Pitilakis, K., 2015. Seismic vulnerability assessment of high-rise
512 non-ductile RC buildings considering soil–structure interaction effects. *Soil Dynamics and Earth-*
513 *quake Engineering* **73**, 42 – 57.

514 Karatzetzou, A. and Pitilakis, D., 2018. Reduction factors to evaluate acceleration demand of soil-
515 foundation-structure systems. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* **109**, 199–208.

516 Karsan, I. and Jirsa, J., 1969. Behavior of concrete under compressive loadings. *Journal of the Structural*
517 *Division* **95**, 2535–2563.

518 Kausel, E., Whitman, R. V., Morray, J. P., and Elsabee, F., 1978. The spring method for embedded
519 foundations. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* **48**, 377–392.

520 Kent, D. C. and Park, R., 1971. Inelastic behavior of reinforced concrete members with cyclic loading.
521 *Bulletin of the New Zealand Society for Earthquake Engineering* **4**, 108–125.

522 Kohrangi, M., Bazzurro, P., Vamvatsikos, D., and Spillatura, A., 2017. Conditional spectrum-based
523 ground motion record selection using average spectral acceleration. *Earthquake Engineering & Struc-*
524 *tural Dynamics* **46**, 1667–1685.

525 Kramer, S. L., 2014. Performance-Based Design Factors for Pile Foundations .

526 Kuhlemeyer, R. and Lysmer, J., 1973. Finite Element Method Accuracy for Wave Propagation Problems.
527 *Journal of the Soil Dynamics Division* **99**, 421–427.

528 Lysmer, J. and Kuhlemeyer, R. L., 1969. Finite dynamic model for infinite media. *Journal of the*
529 *Engineering Mechanics Division* **95**, 859–877.

530 Martins, L., Silva, V., Marques, M., Crowley, H., and Delgado, R., 2016. Development and assessment
531 of damage-to-loss models for moment-frame reinforced concrete buildings. *Earthquake Engineering*
532 *& Structural Dynamics* **45**, 797–817.

533 Mazzoni, S., McKenna, F., Scott, M. H., and Fenves, G. L., 2009. *Open System for Earthquake Engi-*
534 *neering Simulation User Command-Language Manual. Tech. Rep. Pacific Earthquake Engineering*
535 *Research Center, Berkeley, USA.*

536 Miano, A., Jalayer, F., Ebrahimian, H., and Prota, A., 2018. Cloud to IDA: Efficient fragility assessment
537 with limited scaling. *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics* **47**, 1124–1147.

538 Mylonakis, G. and Gazetas, G., 2000. Seismic Soil-Structure Interaction: Beneficial or Detrimental?
539 *Journal of Earthquake Engineering* **4**, 277–301.

540 Mylonakis, G., Nikolaou, S., and Gazetas, G., 2006. Footings under seismic loading: Analysis and
541 design issues with emphasis on bridge foundations. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* **26**,
542 824–853.

- 543 NIST, 2012. *Soil-Structure Interaction for Building Structures*. Tech. rep.
- 544 Pais, A. and Kausel, E., 1988. Approximate formulas for dynamic stiffnesses of rigid foundations. *Soil*
545 *Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* **7**, 213–227.
- 546 Pitilakis, D., Moderessi-Farahmand-Razavi, A., and Clouteau, D., 2013. Equivalent-Linear Dynamic
547 Impedance Functions of Surface Foundations. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engi-*
548 *neering* **139**, 1130–1139.
- 549 Rajeev, P. and Tesfamariam, S., 2012. Seismic fragilities of non-ductile reinforced concrete frames with
550 consideration of soil structure interaction. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* **40**, 78–86.
- 551 Raychowdhury, P., 2011. Seismic response of low-rise steel moment-resisting frame (SMRF) buildings
552 incorporating nonlinear soil-structure interaction (SSI) **33**, 958–967.
- 553 Raychowdhury, P. and Hutchinson, T. C., 2009. Performance evaluation of a nonlinear Winkler-based
554 shallow foundation model using centrifuge test results. *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dy-*
555 *namics* **38**, 679–698.
- 556 Rossetto, T. and Elnashai, A., 2003. Derivation of vulnerability functions for European-type RC struc-
557 tures based on observational data. *Engineering Structures* **25**, 1241–1263.
- 558 Rovithis, E., Kirtas, E., Bliziotis, D., Maltezos, E., Pitilakis, D., Makra, K., Savvaidis, A., Karakostas,
559 C., and Lekidis, V., 2017. A LiDAR-aided urban-scale assessment of soil-structure interaction effects
560 : the case of Kalochori residential area (N. Greece). *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* .
- 561 Saez, E., Lopez-Caballero, F., and Modaressi-Farahmand-Razavi, A., 2011. Effect of the inelastic dy-
562 namic soil–structure interaction on the seismic vulnerability assessment. *Structural Safety* **33**, 51–63.
- 563 Saez, E. R., Lopez-Caballero, F., and Modaressi-Farahmand-Razavi, A., 2008. Effects of non-linear
564 soil behaviour on the seismic performance evaluation of structures. *Rivista Italiana Di Geotecnica* **2**,
565 63–76.
- 566 Scott, B. D., Park, R., and Priestley, M. J. N., 1982. Stress-Strain Behavior of Concrete Confined by
567 Overlapping Hoops at Low and High Strain Rates.
- 568 Silva, V., 2019. Uncertainty and correlation in seismic vulnerability functions of building classes. *Earth-*
569 *quake Spectra* **35**.
- 570 Silva, V., Akkar, S., Baker, J., Bazzurro, P., Castro, J. M., Crowley, H., Dolsek, M., Galasso, C., Lago-
571 marsino, S., Monteiro, R., Perrone, D., Pitilakis, K., and Vamvatsikos, D., 2019. Current Challenges
572 and Future Trends in Analytical Fragility and Vulnerability Modelling. *Earthquake Spectra* **35**, 1927–
573 1952.
- 574 Silva, V., Crowley, H., Pagani, M., Monelli, D., and Pinho, R., 2014. Development of the OpenQuake
575 engine, the Global Earthquake Model’s open-source software for seismic risk assessment. *Natural*
576 *Hazards* **72**, 1409–1427.
- 577 Silva, V. and Horspool, N., 2019. Combining USGS ShakeMaps and the OpenQuake-engine for damage
578 and loss assessment. *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics* pp. 1–19.
- 579 Stewart, J., Fenves, G., and Seed, R., 1999a. Seismic soil-structure interaction in buildings. I: Analytical
580 methods. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering* **125**, 26–37.
- 581 Stewart, J., Seed, R., and Fenves, G., 1999b. Seismic soil-structure interaction in buildings. II: Empirical
582 findings. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering* **125**, 38–48.
- 583 Stewart, J. P., Afshari, K., and Goulet, C. A., 2017. Non-Ergodic Site Response in Seismic Hazard
584 Analysis. *Earthquake Spectra* **33**, 1385–1414. doi:10.1193/081716EQS135M.
- 585 Tang, Y. and Zhang, J., 2011. Probabilistic seismic demand analysis of a slender RC shear wall consid-
586 ering soil–structure interaction effects. *Engineering Structures* **33**, 218 – 229.

- 587 Tomeo, R., Pitilakis, D., Bilotta, A., and Nigro, E., 2018. SSI effects on seismic demand of reinforced
588 concrete moment resisting frames. *Engineering Structures* **173**, 559–572. doi:10.1016/j.engstruct.
589 2018.06.104.
- 590 Vamvatsikos, D. and Cornell, C. A., 2002. Incremental dynamic analysis. *Earthquake Engineering and*
591 *Structural Dynamics* **31**, 491–514.
- 592 Vamvatsikos, D. and Cornell, C. A., 2004. Applied incremental dynamic analysis. *Earthquake Spectra*
593 **20**, 523–553.
- 594 Yang, Z., Lu, J., and Elgamal, A., 2008. *OpenSees Soil Models and Solid-Fluid Fully Coupled Elements*.
595 *Tech. Rep. October*.
- 596 Yepes-Estrada, C., Silva, V., Rossetto, T., D’Ayala, D., Ioannou, I., Meslem, A., and Crowley, H., 2016.
597 The Global Earthquake Model Physical Vulnerability Database. *Earthquake Spectra* **32**, 2567–2585.

599 In this appendix section we provide more details on the models of the buildings, the infills, the
600 soil, and the free-field response spectra that we obtain from the analyses of the soil columns.

601 BUILDINGS

602 We used fiber elements in our models instead of using the plastic hinges approach, as in [Kappos](#)
603 [et al. \(2006\)](#), using the materials described in the main text. Some indicative characteristics
604 are shown in Table 1. Most buildings in the South of Europe built around the 1960s are char-
605 acterized by sparse (>200 mm), **improperly constructed, transverse reinforcement, thus**, this
606 reinforcement is neglected in our analyses. Figure 10 shows the geometry and reinforcement
607 for the selected 2-story building. Further description of the buildings examined in our study can
608 be found in [Kappos et al. \(2003\)](#).

Figure 10. Geometry and reinforcement of the 2-story building.

609 INFILLS

610 Following the procedure described in [Kappos et al. \(2003\)](#), we model the unreinforced masonry
611 infill walls as equivalent strut models. In particular, we use the "truss" element provided in
612 OpenSees to model the equivalent strut, as well as the corresponding skeleton curve of the
613 hysteresis model, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Sketch representing the RC frame and unreinforced masonry infill (left). Equivalent strut model (right).

614 The axial stiffness coefficient of the equivalent strut is estimated as a function of the shear
 615 stiffness of the infill wall and the inclination of the strut, as shown in Equation 3.

$$E_S \cdot A_S = \frac{G_w \cdot A_w}{\cos^2 a \cdot \sin a} \quad (3)$$

616 SOIL

617 Table 5 shows the suggested parameter values, as found in OpenSees wiki. In our work, we
 618 implement the soil models described in the main text adapting these values for the parameters
 619 involved. In particular, upon selecting a specific value for the shear wave velocity characterizing
 620 the soil profile, we use Equation 4 to estimate the corresponding soil shear modulus. To adapt
 621 the values proposed in Table 5, we use linear interpolation between the values, with respect to
 622 the shear moduli estimated.

$$G = V_s^2 \cdot \rho \quad (4)$$

Table 5. Suggested soil parameter values in OpenSees, as reported in the software wiki adapted from the USCD soil models. These values are initially reported in [Das \(1983\)](#); [Holtz and Kovacs \(1981\)](#); [Das \(1981\)](#), and should be used with caution and engineering judgement.

Parameters	Soft Clay	Medium Clay	Stiff Clay
Soil mass density	1.3 ton/m ³	1.5 ton/m ³	1.8 ton/m ³
Low-strain shear modulus	1.3x10 ⁴ kPa	6.0x10 ⁴ kPa	1.5x10 ⁵ kPa
Bulk modulus	6.5x10 ⁴ kPa	3.0x10 ⁵ kPa	7.5x10 ⁵ kPa
Cohesion	18 kPa	37 kPa	75 kPa
Shear strain at max shear	0.1	0.1	0.1
Friction angle	0.0	0.0	0.0

623 **RESPONSE SPECTRA**

624 Indicatively, we present in Figures 12, 13 and 14 the normalized response spectra at the free
625 field, for the soil profiles 2 ($V_{s,30} = 450m/s$), 3 ($V_{s,30} = 360m/s$), 5 ($V_{s,30} = 250m/s$) and
626 6 ($V_{s,30} = 180m/s$) according to Table 2, for PGA at bedrock level equal to 1 m/s², 3 m/s²
627 and 7 m/s², respectively. Thick lines are the mean spectra, while light grey lines are the clouds
628 of the free-field responses. In the same figures, we plot in colored lines the normalized EC8
629 response spectra referring to soil types B, C and D. We observe that, indeed, soil amplification
630 is generally higher for lower PGA at bedrock.

Figure 12. Normalized response spectra at the free field for the soil profiles 2, 3, 5 and 6 according to Table 2, for PGA at bedrock level equal to 1 m/s^2 , and the corresponding mean spectra and normalized EC8 response spectra referring to soil types B, C and D.

Figure 13. Normalized response spectra at the free field for the soil profiles 2, 3, 5 and 6 according to Table 2, for PGA at bedrock level equal to 3 m/s^2 , and the corresponding mean spectra and normalized EC8 response spectra referring to soil types B, C and D.

Figure 14. Normalized response spectra at the free field for the soil profiles 2, 3, 5 and 6 according to Table 2, for PGA at bedrock level equal to 7 m/s^2 , and the corresponding mean spectra and normalized EC8 response spectra referring to soil types B, C and D.